

Role of Commerce Education in Achieving Sustainable Development Goals

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.1939887

Abstract:

In 2015, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were adopted by the United Nations aim to achieve inclusive growth, environmental sustainability and social justice by 2030. To achieve these goals primarily Education plays a vital role and commerce education is particularly significant due to its connection with business practices, finance, accounts, taxation and economic systems.

This paper examines how commerce education contributes to achieve some Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), such as economic growth, poverty reduction, gender equality, responsible consumption and climate action. The study is based on secondary data collected from academic literature, Journals, policy reports. The present study concludes that a powerful tool for sustainable and inclusive growth is a Commerce Education.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Inclusive growth, financial literacy, commerce Education.

Introduction:

Sustainable Development has emerged as a global priority in the 21st century. Due to rapid industrialization, population growth and environmental degradation, Sustainable Development has gained global importance. The idea of Sustainable Development focuses on balancing economic growth, environmental protection and social welfare. So, the global community recognized these challenges and adopted Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015.

Education plays a transformative role in achieving these above goals. Traditionally, commerce education focused on profit maximization and business growth. Commerce education consists disciplines such as finance, economics, taxation, banking, marketing, accounting, entrepreneurship, business law and management. It develops the student's financial literacy, analytical skills and ethical decision

making abilities which is necessary for sustainable economic development. In recent years, commerce education has evolved to include concepts such as Corporate Social Responsibility, sustainable finance, green accounting and environmental governance. Therefore commerce education must prepare students to integrate sustainability principles into business practices. This paper throw light on commerce education in achieving selected SDGs and examines how curriculum reforms, sustainable finance practice, and ethical business models are important for inclusive growth.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the concept and significance of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
2. To examine the role commerce education in Sustainable Economic Development

3. To evaluate how commerce education contributes to selected Sustainable Development Goals

Research Methodology:

This paper is based on secondary data collected from books, academic journals, government reports and publications related to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and commerce education. The present research study follows descriptive method and analytical approach to examine theoretical perspective and practical applications of commerce education in achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Concept of Sustainable Development Goals:

Sustainable Development refers to a development model that ensures economic growth while protecting environmental resources and promoting social equality. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), provide 17 interconnected goals addressing poverty, inequality, environmental degradation, climate change peace and justice. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are given below.

- No Poverty – End Poverty in all forms
- Zero hunger – End hunger and ensure food security
- Good health and well-being – Ensure healthy lives for all
- Quality education – Provide inclusive and equitable education
- Gender equality – Achieve equality for women and girls
- Clean water and sanitization – Ensure access to safe water and sanitization
- Affordable and clean energy – Provide sustainable energy for all
- Decent work and economic growth – Promote employment and economic growth

- Industry, innovation and infrastructure – Build resilient infrastructure and promote innovation
- Reduced inequalities – Reduce inequality within and among countries.
- Sustainable cities and communities – Make cities safe and sustainable
- Responsible consumption and production – Use resources efficiently
- Climate action – Take urgent action against climate change.
- Life below water – Protect oceans and marine resources.
- Life and land – Protect forests, biodiversity and ecosystems.
- Peace, justice and strong institutions – Promote peaceful societies and justice.
- Partnerships for the goals –Strengthen global partnerships.

Achieving these goals require participation from various sectors of society, including governments, businesses and educational institutions.

Key features of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

- Adopted in 2015
- Target year 2030
- Total 17 goals, 169 targets and 232 indicators
- Applies to all countries
- Focus on People, Planet, Prosperity, Peace and Partnership(5Ps)

Significance of Commerce Education:

Commerce education plays vital role in economies because it focuses on the management of financial economic resources. Commerce education enhances the knowledge of business management, finance, banking, economics, market, taxation, and financial market.

The significance of commerce education are as follows.

- It develop managerial and entrepreneurial skills
- It prepares skilled professionals for corporate and public sectors
- It develops economic awareness and financial literacy among the students
- It prepares professionals for banking business, corporate management and public administration.
- It encourages ethical decision making in business operation and corporate governance

As India moves forward sustainable development, commerce education helps to train professionals who can balance economic growth with environmental and social responsibility.

Major Three dimensions:

Commerce education contributes to Sustainable Development through three major dimensions which are as follows

- Economic Sustainability - financial growth, promoting growth and entrepreneurship
- Social Sustainability – Encouraging equity, gender equality and ethical governance
- Environmental Sustainability supporting green accounting and sustainable finance

Role of Commerce education in achieving selected Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

- **SDG 1 – POVERTY Reduction and financial inclusion:** Commerce education helps promote financial awareness/literacy, access to banking services and entrepreneurship, enabling individuals to create employment opportunities and improve economic growth. Knowledge of financial management, microfinance, and digital payments support government initiatives

aimed at reducing poverty and improving financial inclusion

- **SDG 4 – quality education and skill development:** Commerce education enhances professional skills and practical knowledge related to accounting, taxation, financial markets, and entrepreneurship that improves employability. Skill based education contributes to economic development and social progress.
- **SDG 5 – Gender Equality:** Commerce education empowers women by providing knowledge and skills necessary for financial independence and entrepreneurship. Women with business and financial knowledge are more likely to participate in economic decision-making and leadership roles. Increased participation of women in business activities contributes to gender equality.
- **SDG 8 – decent work and economic growth:** Entrepreneurship education encourages innovation, business creation and job generation. Commerce graduates contribute to economic growth and development through effective financial planning and management
- **SDG 9 – Industry Innovation and Infrastructure:** Commerce professionals play a key role in business planning, project evaluation, and market research. These activities support industrial growth, technological innovation and infrastructure development.
- **SDG 12 – Responsible consumption and production:** Commerce education provides the knowledge of corporate social responsibility, ethical business practices, green accounting and sustainable supply chain management which promote efficient use of resources and reduce environmental impact.

- **SDG 13 – climate action and environmental responsibility:** Commerce education provides knowledge related to sustainable finance, green accounting and environmental accounting. It encourages companies to adopt Eco-friendly practices and reduce their ecological impact.

Findings of the Study:

- The study reveals that commerce education contributes significantly to sustainable development by promoting financial literacy/awareness, ethical governance and responsible business practices.
- Commerce education also supports entrepreneurship, employment generation/job creation and inclusive economic growth.

Challenges:

Despite its potential, several challenges limit the effectiveness of commerce education in promoting sustainability. Challenges are as follows.

- Limited integration of sustainability topics in traditional curriculum.
- Lack of practical exposure to sustainable business models.
- Insufficient collaboration between universities and industries.

Suggestions:

To strengthen the role of commerce education in achieving SDGs, the following measures are recommended

- Incorporate sustainability concepts into commerce curriculum
- Encourage research on sustainable business practices.

- Promote internship and industry collaborations.
- Provide training programs on sustainable finance, green accounting and ESG reporting (Environmental, Social and Governance Report)

Conclusion:

Commerce education plays significant role in achieving Sustainable Development Goals by promoting responsible economic practices, financial literacy and ethical governance. It prepare students to become responsible professionals who contribute to economic growth and development while protecting environmental resources and promoting social welfare. Strengthening sustainability education within commerce programs will help to create future business leaders capable of addressing global challenge and building a sustainable economy.

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